

SELF-GOVERNANCE OF CITIZENS IN UZBEKISTAN LEGAL BASIS OF
AUTHORITIES.

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Key words: Citizen self-management bodies, state administration, state power, neighborhood, village, village, law, legislative documents, subordinate documents, social class, sphere of authority.

Abstract: In this article, no matter how democratic the independence of self-government is, it cannot be absolute independence, because self-government must exist and operate within the system of public power relations within a single state, certain independence in solving local issues cannot be denied, but it is a single state it is shown that it cannot be carried out outside the direction of economic, social, ideological policy.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" defines the status of self-governing bodies in the state administration system [1] (Article 8) and states that self-governing bodies of citizens do not belong to the system of local government bodies. This rule, which is based on the interaction of self-governing bodies and their officials with state bodies and their officials, provides that the structure, designation, scope of authority of self-governing bodies are determined independently, without the intervention of the state, in a way that meets local interests.

Different opinions about the nature of self-government, its interaction with state power not reported. No matter how democratic the self-governance independence is, it cannot be absolute independence, because self-governance exists within the system of public power relations within the framework of a single state and, in fact, solves local issues. a certain independence cannot be denied, but it cannot be transferred outside the direction of the economic, social, ideological policy of the single state. Is it possible to imagine the vital interests of people outside the interests of the state and the daily work of the residents of towns, villages and neighborhoods? In Article 13 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (revised in 2021) [2], the state itself declares that "a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are the highest value".

Self-government cannot be outside the relations of the state system and - Power cannot be completely independent from the State. Most of the objective principles inherent in the current state of self-government in the state mechanism indicate that the interests of the state cannot be opposed to local interests, because these interests cannot conflict with each other[3:22]. Both state interests and local interests are actually common interests of the country. In Article 8 of the Law "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens", the provision that these bodies are not included in the system of state authorities, in our opinion, is an attempt to separate self-governing bodies from state bodies, to emphasize the social nature of self-governing bodies. This rule is more of a political nature than a clear legal reality

It is very difficult to express it in language. In the first article of the law, self-government of citizens is guaranteed by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on their own interests, historical [4:1492-1495] characteristics of development, as well as national and spiritual values , local customs and traditions. The rule that it is independent activity in solving issues is also a proof of this opinion.

At the same time, there are some problems[5:135-138] and complications in the relationship between the state and self-government. Independence and centralization, self-management and state power are incompatible concepts, moreover, mistakes and shortcomings made by state bodies and officials in the implementation of public policy in the field of self-management complicate the relationship between them, and as a result, some difficulties arise.

Unfortunately, it should be noted that mandatory requirements for legislative activities are not always followed[6:1-6]. As a result, some laws in this field do not comply with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, it is self-evident that efforts to regulate issues of local importance, which are the competence of self-governing bodies, the procedure for determining the forms of direct participation of the population in solving local issues, and the rules for conducting elections for citizens' self-governing bodies [7:121-123] are frequent shortcomings in the field of management legislation. The nature and content of the deficiencies found in the laws in this area is self-management contradicting the rules on the independence and initiative of the bodies, which creates additional difficulties in the way of establishing and improving these bodies.

Self-government has a number of characteristics characteristic of state power: among others, there is a separate apparatus that exercises power in its territory, their activities continue continuously and universally, they are based on laws and regulatory documents, they control the administration in a specific area [8:96-100] implements, makes a decision to collect a voluntary fee from the population, forms its own budget. At the same time, the self-governing territory [9:128-131] is a state is the territory, and the population living in it are citizens of this country. Several other circumstances should be taken into account: the status of self-government is determined by the state in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and laws adopted by state authorities; their status is protected by state authorities; local affairs are resolved independently, but in the direction of a single [10:396-400] state policy; the decisions of local self-government bodies must be executed by all relevant persons and institutions; some powers of the state may be transferred to self-governing bodies, etc.

In addition, self-governing bodies do not have the right to exercise their legislative authority [11:73-76]. The absence of the right to legislate for one's territory to replace general laws on these issues is an important criterion that distinguishes self-government from state power. Self-governing bodies can issue normative documents that describe the rules of action of a general nature [12:26-28], of course.

But these documents, by their nature, are bylaws, not laws. Lack of strict classification and mutual subordination in their system when justifying the non-state character of self-governing bodies; that they do not act on behalf of the state; to resolve issues of local importance [13:26] based on the development characteristics of their territory; to organize their material and financial basis in self-management property and budget; they are shown as proof of such signs as being very close to the population.

Thus, it should be noted that the self-governing authority [14:62] consists of a unique system of power relations, and the tasks of local self-governing are carried out through its own apparatus. It is a type of social and at the same time public power (power over society) and operates within the framework of self-management structures. This activity is carried out by self-governing bodies on behalf of the local structure and on the basis of legal norms. Self-governing power can be defined as a form of social relations that corresponds to the norms that determine the status of a local structure.

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